

Advances of MetaDocencia's new governance

During the second half of 2022 we began to collaboratively develop our governance. We intended to design a transparent model for strategic decision-making that would allow us to strengthen our institutional mission based on community building.

This purpose brought us together in a collective learning process, through open conversations with invited specialists and a large number of team meetings to present, process, and shape the different stages of our institutional documents. Many people contributed to the discussion, helping us imagine, learn and think about new forms of organization and management models for open education and knowledge spaces.

The path we are following is a process of creation, in which we seek to formalize and document agreements regarding the operational and decision-making structures that will give MetaDocencia a solid structure that can transcend people.

The challenge is to generate an autonomous, sustainable, and ordered space to work and grow, while preserving the flexibility, openness, and permeability required for the production, communication, and application of scientific and technical knowledge in a fluid and hyperconnected world.

We plan to review this governance after the first year of implementation. It will also represent a challenge to keep an open perspective and allow us to question what might not be working.

We will soon communicate and share with other communities the organizational model we are thinking for MetaDocencia, designed for and shaped by our cultural and regional context.

Our greatest expectation is that our journey contributes to strengthening other communities around the world, as well as public and open spaces for knowledge, exchange, networking, and collaboration.

Finally, we hope that the implementation of our new governance will be the beginning of a process of open exchange and dialogue, which will help continue to build community based on our values, mission, and vision for the future 🙌🌱 .